

declined at the Makassa farm, site of the upland experimental fields of the Rokupr Station, where rice had been continuously planted since 1974. The 1978 crop was markedly stunted, and affected plants had short, fibrous, and discolored roots. The long, plump, and light-colored roots typical of healthy plants were conspicuously absent.

The following parasitic species were found in soil samples examined:

Nematode	No./liter
<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp.	262
<i>Helicotylenchus</i> sp.	174
<i>Rotylenchulus</i> sp.	178
<i>Criconemoides</i> sp.	115
<i>Tylenchus</i> sp.	67
<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp.	39
Total	835

The exact influence of the nematodes on the decline in plant growth and vigor has not yet been determined. In a 1978 test, yields of plots treated with the soil fumigant D-D were four times those of untreated control plots.

The soil pH at the site declined from about pH 5.2 in 1974 to pH 4.2 in 1978. Other organisms, including fungi and bacteria, were also isolated from the roots of affected plants.

F. E. Caveness, nematologist, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, assisted in identifying the nematodes. ■

Relationship between incidence of brown planthopper and rice stem rot pathogen

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The exploratory, feeding, and ovipositional punctures of the brown planthopper (BPH) seem to predispose rice plants to fungal and bacterial infections. Although information on this possibility is not definite, infection of BPH-infested plants by two mold fungi — *Cladosporium* sp. and *Dematium* sp. — has been reported. Stem rot disease caused by *Sclerotium oryzae* Tullis, a wound pathogen, might

Correlation between brown planthopper (BPH) and stem rot disease, Annamalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu, 1973 kuruvai.

Productive tillers (no.)	BPH adults and nymphs (no.)	Sclerotia (no.)	BPH location from plant base (cm)
8	17	7	5
7	27	10	10
9	40	10	12
8	40	58	10
7	47	50	12
8	50	50	8
9	51	50	15
11	55	100	12
14	55	170	15
9	62	70	18
11	65	70	10
6	80	75	8
9	87	75	10
12	90	70	15
15	100	140	10
8	105	150	12
5	107	140	10
8	110	120	8
9	127	155	15
7	160	170	12

occur in BPH-damaged portions of the plant. Therefore, a study was conducted in 1974 kuruvai to determine possible relationships between BPH population and incidence of stem rot pathogen.

Twenty hills of the variety Triveni with high BPH populations and stem rot incidence were selected at the Annamalai University Experimental Farm. Adult and nymph hoppers and black bodies (sclerotia) were counted and the total number was used as the criterion for indexing.

The correlation between the BPH

population and the fungal disease was positive ($r = 0.80^{**}$). Because the stem rot pathogen is basically a wound parasite, its occurrence might be facilitated by damage from insects, by lodging, or by other injuries. The increases in BPH population coincide with increases in sclerotia number (see table).

Thus, when BPH occurs, efforts to combat the stem rot pathogen might be initiated along with BPH control measures. ■

Effect of fungicides on disease control in dapog

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Fungicidal control of rice seedling diseases in a dapog nursery was evaluated in December 1978. Seeds were sown at 1 kg/m². Fungicides were applied as a) a 12-hour wet-seed treatment b) a foliar spray at 10 clays after sowing (DS), and c) a soil drench at 10 DS. At 25 DS, the seedlings were observed for infection by diseases caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Fusarium* spp.,

Effect of fungicides on seedling infection in rice, Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Mean seedling infection ^a (%)		
	12-h wet-seed treatment	Foliar spray 10-DS	Soil drenching 10 DS
• <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> spp., <i>Phythium</i> spp. ^b			
Hinosan	30.7	31.2	34.0
Dithane R-24	32.3	29.6	40.5
Bavistin	39.2	30.1	32.3
Fytolan	32.7	26.6	43.6
Agallol	16.6	27.8	34.1
Difolatan	32.8	27.4	32.7
Control	44.3	44.3	44.3
• <i>Pyricularia oryzae</i> ^c			
Hinosan	34.23	41.39	13.48
Dithane R-24	20.55	17.27	12.31

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Effect of fungicides. . . . cont.

Fungicide	Mean Seedling infection ^a (%)		
	12-h wet-seed treatment	Foliar spray 10 DS	Soil drenching 10 DS
Bavistin	11.84	11.16	12.38
Fytolan	38.44	36.81	24.03
Agallol	53.07	39.42	28.17
Difolatan	55.64	45.72	27.82
Control	58.77	58.77	58.77

^aDS = days after seeding, ^bS.E. = 4.51, C.D. = 13.40, ^cS.E. = 6.07, C.D. = 18.01.

Phythium spp., and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

The wet-seed treatment with Agallol most effectively controlled seedling diseases caused by *R. solani*, *Fusarium* spp., and *Phythium* spp. (see table). All three treatments with Bavistin best controlled blast caused by *P. oryzae*. Chemical control of rice seedling diseases in dapog culture appears promising. ■

Egg parasites of the yellow stem borer in West Bengal

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Natural enemies play an important role in the control of populations of the rice yellow borer *Tryporyza incertulas* (Wlk.). They should be considered for maintaining homeostasis, particularly in the wet season when chemical protection is neither economical nor feasible in low-lying areas of West Bengal. Egg parasites are important components in the faunal composition of natural enemies. Five hymenopteran insects have been noted on yellow borer egg masses at the Chinsurah Station and identified from IBP Handbook 14 as *Tetrastichus schoenobii* Ferr., *Telenomus dignus* Gahan, *Telenomus dignoides* Nixon, *Telenomus rowani* Gahan, and *Trichogramma japonicum* Ashm. The percentage of parasitism was estimated from the emergence of parasitoids from the viable eggs of field-collected egg masses (see table).

The low parasitism in March and April

Egg parasitization of the yellow stem borer at Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Month	Egg masses (no.)	Sterile egg masses (no.)	Parasitized egg masses (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Feb	136	24	70	62
Mar	117	25	48	52
Apr	136	34	41	40
May	44	24	14	71
Jun	45	10	12	34
Jul	36	2	16	48
Aug	26	2	17	71
Sep	35	2	21	63
Oct	137	9	70	55
Nov	164	54	98	89

and high parasitism in May and August suggest that parasitoid activity might not be dependent on the density of egg masses in the field. Sterility in borer egg masses was caused by high temperature, particularly in May. Many parasitoids could not emerge from eggs when the air temperature was higher than 32°C. ■

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Effect of seedling density on gall midge infestation and rice yields in northern Thailand

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Rice generally tillers profusely and yields several times more in northern Thailand – where soils are relatively fertile and rain is uniform throughout the growing season - than in the northeast. Previous studies indicated that rice yields under gall midge-infested conditions in the northeast can be increased by planting more seedlings per hill. A study was conducted to determine if seedling density could be increased in the north.

The experiment was in a randomized complete block design, replicated three times. Niew Sanpatawng, a susceptible traditional variety, was transplanted in

4- x 6-m² plots in a farmer's field at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai province. The seedlings were transplanted 3, 5, and 7/hill at 25-x 25-cm spacing and at 3/hill at 15- x 15-cm spacing. Gall midge-damaged tillers were counted at the peak of infestation (20 Sep 1978).

Rice planted at high seedling density had a higher percentage of damaged tillers (see table). The average numbers of tillers and panicles did not differ significantly among the treatments at 25- x 25-cm spacing, but they differed from the averages for rice planted at 15 x 15 cm. The yield of rice planted at 3 seedlings/hill at 25- x 25-cm spacing was highest, but it was not significantly higher than that of the other treatments at that spacing. The results do not agree with our past observations in the northeast – probably because the high-tillering rice in the north can rapidly compensate for gall midge-damaged tillers. ■

Gall midge infestation, yield components, and grain yields of Niew Sanpatawng rice planted at different numbers of seedlings per hill and different spacings at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, Thailand, 1978.

Treatment		Damaged tillers (%)	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)
Spacing (cm)	Seedlings (no./hill)				
15 x 15	3	34	4.8	3.2	3.4
25 x 25	3	23	9.0	6.9	5.0
25 x 25	5	25	9.4	7.2	4.6
25 x 25	7	32	9.5	7.1	4.9
LSD (5%)		6.6	0.73	0.73	0.7